

약학석사학위논문

췌장암의 화학적 성분 및 Tyrosinase 저해 활성

Chemical constituents and Tyrosinase Inhibitory Activity of

Lycopus lucidus

충북대학교대학원

약학부 신약개발전공

지텐드라 판데 (Jitendra Pandey)

2018년 2월

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CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES	I
LIST OF TABLES	III
LIST OF ABBRIVIATIONS	IV
ABSTRACT	V
1. Introduction.....	1
1.1 <i>Lycopus lucidus</i>	1
1.2 Melanogenesis.....	5
1.3 The objective of this study	7
2. Experiments	8
2.1 Materials	8
2.1.1 Plant material of <i>Lycopus lucidus</i>	8
2.2.2 Reagents	8
2.2.2.1 Reagents for isolation	8
2.2 Instruments.....	8
2.3 Extraction and isolation of <i>Lycopus lucidus</i>	10
2.4 Compound separation from ethyl acetate fraction.....	11
2.5 Biological activity.....	14
2.5.1 Tyrosinase enzyme activity assay.....	14
3. Result and Discussion	15
3.1. NMR data of known compounds.....	15
3.1.1 Protocatechuic acid (1).....	15
3.1.2 Protocatechualdehyde (2).....	15
3.1.3 Methyl 3, 4 dihydroxy benzoate (3)	15
3.1.4 Para-hydroxy benzoic acid (4).....	16
3.1.5 Caffeic acid (5)	16

3.1.6 Rosmarinic acid (6)	16
3.1.7 Methyl rosmarinate (7)	17
3.1.8 Quercetin 3- <i>O</i> - β -D-glucopyranoside (8)	17
3.1.9 Luteolin (11).....	18
3.2 Structure elucidation of new compounds from <i>Lycopus lucidus</i>	19
3.2.1 Structure elucidation of compound 9	19
3.1.2 Structure elucidation of compound 10.....	30
3.2.3 Structure elucidation of compound 12	41
3.2.4 Structure elucidation of compound 13	51
3.2.5 Structure elucidation of compound 14.....	62
3.3 Tyrosinase enzyme inhibition by isolated compounds.....	74
4. Conclusion.....	77
5. Appendix.....	78
6. References:.....	96

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: a. Aerial parts b. Whole plant c. Dried aerial parts d. herbarium of <i>Lycopus lucidus</i>	2
Figure 2: Chemical constituents of <i>Lycopus lucidus</i>	3
Figure 3: Signal pathways for melanogenesis.....	6
Figure 4:Schematic diagram of extraction and fractionation of aerial parts of <i>Lycopus lucidus</i>	10
Figure 5:Schematic diagram of extraction and isolation of compounds from aerial parts of <i>Lycopus lucidus</i>	13
Figure 6: ¹³ C- NMR of compound 9 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄).....	23
Figure 7:- ¹ H- NMR of compound 9 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄).....	24
Figure 8: Mass spectrum of compound 9.....	25
Figure 9: HMQC spectrum of compound 9 400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄).....	26
Figure 10: COSY spectrum of compound 9 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄).....	27
Figure 11: HMBC spectrum of compound 9 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄).....	28
Figure 12: ROESY spectrum of compound 9 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄) (3β, 8β, 12β, 18-tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en).....	29
Figure 13: ¹³ C- NMR of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	34
Figure 14: ¹ H- NMR of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	35
Figure 15: Mass spectrum of compound 10.....	36
Figure 16: HMQC spectrum of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	37
Figure 17: COSY spectrum of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	38
Figure 18: ROESY spectrum of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄) (7α, 8β, 12β, 18-tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en).....	40
Figure 19: ¹³ C- NMR of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	44
Figure 20: ¹ H- NMR of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	45
Figure 21: Mass Spectrum of compound 12	46
Figure 22: HMQC Correlation of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	47
Figure 23: COSY Correlation of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄).....	48
Figure 24: HMBC Correlation of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	49
Figure 25: ROESY Correlation of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol-	

<i>d</i> ₄) (3β, 8β, 11β, 12α, 18-pentahydroxy pimar-15-en).....	50
Figure 26: ¹³ C- NMR of compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	55
Figure 27: ¹ H- NMR of compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	56
Figure 28: Mass spectrum of compound 13	57
Figure 29: HMQC spectrum compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄).....	58
Figure 30: COSY Correlation of compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄).....	59
Figure 31: HMBC Correlation of compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄)	60
Figure 32: ROESY Correlation of compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄) (12β acetoxy, 8β, 3β, 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en).....	61
Figure 33: ¹³ C- NMR of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- <i>d</i> ₆)	66
Figure 34: ¹ H- NMR of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- <i>d</i> ₆)	67
Figure 35: Mass spectrum of compound 14.....	68
Figure 36: HMQC Correlation of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- <i>d</i> ₆)	69
Figure 37: COSY Correlation of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- <i>d</i> ₆).....	70
Figure 38: HMBC Correlation of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- <i>d</i> ₆)	71
Figure 39:- ROESY Correlation of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- <i>d</i> ₆) (3β acetoxy, 8β, 12β, 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en)	72
Figure 40: Compounds isolated from ethyl acetate fraction of aerial parts of <i>Lycopus lucidus</i>	73
Figure 42: Inhibition percentage of tyrosinase enzyme activity by isolated compounds in at 2 50 μl/ml and 100 μ/ml.....	75

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: The biological activities of representative constituents from <i>Lycopus lucidus</i> in the literatures	4
Table 2: ¹ H and ¹³ C-NMR spectroscopic data of compound 9 in Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄	21
Table 3: ¹ H and ¹³ C-NMR spectroscopic data of compound 10 in Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄	32
Table 4: ¹ H and ¹³ C-NMR spectroscopic data of compound 12 in Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄	43
Table 5: ¹ H and ¹³ C-NMR spectroscopic data of compound 12 in Methanol- <i>d</i> ₄	53
Table 6: ¹ H and ¹³ C-NMR spectroscopic data compound 14 in Acetone- <i>d</i> ₆	64
Table 7: Effect of compounds on tyrosinase enzyme activity in percentage at different concentration.	74

LIST OF ABBRIVIATIONS

RP: Reverse phase

NP: Normal phase

TLC: Thin layer chromatography

Fr: Fraction

EtOAc: Ethyl acetate

UV: Ultra violet

HPLC: High performance liquid chromatography

NMR: Nuclear magnetic resonance

1D, 2D NMR: One dimensional, two dimensional NMR

CDCl₃: deuterated chloroform

CD₃OD: deuterated methanol

DMSO-*d*₆: deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide

Acetone-*d*₆: deuterated acetone

HMQC: Heteronuclear multiple quantum coherence

HMBC: Heteronuclear multiple bond correlation

COSY: Correlation spectroscopy

ROSEY:: Rotational Frame Nuclear Overhauser Effect Chromatography

HR-ESI-MS: High resolution electrospray ionization mass spectrometry

EI-MS: Electron ionization mass spectrometry

Chemical Constituents and Tyrosinase Inhibitory activity of *Lycopus lucidus*

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ABSTRACT

The genus *Lycopus* of family Lamiaceae (Labiatae) contains around 16 species with wide distribution in China, Japan, Russia, Korea, Taiwan, Europe, and North America. Traditionally, leaf, stem (aerial part) and root of *Lycopus lucidus* have been extensively used for the treatment of inflammation, cardiovascular problem, insomnia, irregular menstruation, as sedative, wound healing and pain relieving agents. Biological activities such as hypercholesterolemia, immunological effect, anticancer and antimicrobial effect, anti-allergic activity have been explored from this plant. To investigate anti-melanogenic compounds, dried powder of aerial parts was extracted with methanol. The methanolic extract was fractionated with hexane, ethyl acetate butanol and water. Ethyl acetate fraction was subjected for isolation by using different chromatographic technique such as reverse phase open column chromatography, silica gel open column chromatography and preparative liquid

chromatography, which enabled isolation of five new pimarane type diterpenoids namely 3 β , 8 β , 12 β , 18-tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en (**9**), 7 α , 8 β , 12 β , 18-tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en (**10**), 3 β , 8 β , 11 β , 12 α , 18-pentahydroxy pimar-15-en (**12**), 12 β acetoxy, 8 β , 3 β , 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en (**13**), 3 β acetoxy, 8 β , 12 β , 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en (**14**) and nine known compounds, namely protocatechuic acid (**1**), protocatechualdehyde (**2**), methyl 3,4 dihydroxy benzoate (**3**), para-hydroxy benzoic acid (**4**), caffeic acid (**5**), rosmarinic acid (**6**), methyl rosmarinate (**7**), quercetin 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (**8**) and luteolin (**11**), of these, protocatechualdehyde (**2**) and methyl 3,4 dihydroxy benzoate (**4**) were reported for the first time from this plant. Structure of these compounds was confirmed on the basis of Mass spectroscopy and NMR analysis (^1H , ^{13}C , HMQC, HMBS, COSY, DEPT, and ROESY). After screening of tyrosinase enzyme activity for the isolated compounds, protocatechualdehyde (**2**) and methyl rosmarinate (**7**) showed good inhibitory effect as compare to positive control arbutin.

1. Introduction

1.1 *Lycopus lucidus*.

The genus *Lycopus* of family Lamiaceae (Labiatae) contains around 16 species with wide distribution in Europe, Asia and North America ¹. In Asia, distribution of *Lycopus lucidus* is restricted in China, Japan, Russia, Korea and Taiwan and it is most abundant species in Korea ². Only four species have been reported in Korea till now; *Lycopus maackianus* (Maxim. Ex Herder) Makino (Ae-gi-swip-ssa-ri'), *Lycopus cavaleriei* H. Lev (Gae-swip-ssa-ri'), *Lycopus uniflorus* Michx. (Teol-swip-ssa-ri') and *Lycopus lucidus* (swip-ssa-ri').. *Lycopus lucidus* is a perennial glabrous herb occurring in aquatic environment and grows up to 0.6-1.2 m in height ^{3,4,5}. Pinnatifid or dentate leaves with oblong-lanceolate to ovate lanceolate shape, sessile or very short petiole, ciliate bract, five lobed calyx and four lobed corolla with densely flowered inflorescence, corolla exerted stamen and style and one-seeded nutlet are some diagnostic features of this plant ^{4,5}. Many plants from this genus have been used as both traditional and official formulation as they are potent source of bioactive tannins, coumarins, flavonoids, terpenoids and essential oils ^{3,6}. Among them, *Lycopus lucidus* is one of the popular edible ethno medicinal plants with its long history in traditional medicinal system of China, Japan and Korea ⁷. Leaf and stem (aerial part) of *Lycopus lucidus* has been extensively used for the treatment of inflammation, cardiovascular problem, insomnia, menstrual problems, thyroid problem and also as sedative, wound healing, pain reliving agents, herbal tea and useful tonic ^{6,8,9}. The root of *Lycopus lucidus* is known as small ginseng in the China and widely used as dietary supplement ⁸. Many Biological activities such as inhibition of superoxide radical ⁵, nitric oxide scavenging effect ⁶, inhibition of hypercholesterolemia and atherosclerosis ¹¹,

acaridial activities ¹², hyaluronidase inhibition ⁷ have been explored from this plant. Diverse biological activity in this plant is due to the presence of different classes of bio active compounds such as flavonoid and its esters, rosmarinic acid derivatives, phenylpropanoid, steroids, pentacyclitriterpene, essential oils, oligosaccharides, polysaccharides and diterpenoid glycoside^{3, 6, 8, 9, 21}.

Figure 1: a. Aerial parts b. Whole plant c. Dried aerial parts d. herbarium of *Lycopus lucidus*.

Luteolin

Chrysoeriol

Acacetin

Apigenin

R= H-Quercetin

R= β -D- Glucopyranoside- Quercetin 3-O- β -D-
Glucopyranoside

R=H- Rosmarinic acid

R=CH₃-Methyl rosmarinate

R=CH₂CH₃-Ethyl rosmarinate

Ursolic acid

R= OH-Betulin

R= COOH-Betulinic acid

Caffeic acid

Methyl caffeate

Figure 2: Chemical constituents of *Lycopus lucidus*

Table 1: The biological activities of representative constituents from *Lycopus lucidus* in the literatures

Compounds	Biological activity
Ursolic acid, betulinic acid, betulin and oleanolic acid	Human ACAT-1 and ACAT-2 Inhibitory Activities ¹¹ Inotropic effect ¹⁴
Essential oils such as 1-octen-3-ol and 3,7 dimethyl-1-octen-3-ol,	Acaricidal activities ¹²
Essential oils	Free radical scavenging activity ⁶
Methnanolic extract	Anti-allergic activity Degranulation inhibitory activity ¹³
Monosaccharides oligosaccharides	Immunological effect ²¹
Alpha-humulene	Anti-cancer Activity
Beta-caryophyllene	Antimicrobial activity ¹⁰
Aqueous plant extract	Cell Adhesion Molecule Activity ²² High glucose-induced vascular inflammation inhibition ¹⁵
Methanolic extract	Inhibition of primary dysmenorrhea ²³
Ethanolic extract	Effect on cardiovascular and cerebrovascular disease ²⁴
Rosmarinic acid derivatives	Anti-oxidant activity Hyaluronidase inhibitory activities ⁷ Inotropic effect ¹³

1.2 Melanogenesis

Melanocytes are located at epidermal-dermal junction through which pigment granules i.e. eumelanin and pheomelanin are transferred in to keratinocyte cells for coloration of hair and skins ²⁶. Optimal concentration of melanin pigment in the epidermal cell is beneficial as it protect skin against harmful effect of ultraviolet (UV) radiation but there may be abnormal change in melanin content such as overproduction and accumulation of pigments caused by ageing, metabolic disorders, hormonal changes, skin irritation or other underlying problems. Diseases such as age spots, melasma, freckles, lentigos, beckers nervus and macules due to peutz jeghers syndrome are examples of hyper pigmentation. Hypo pigmentation i.e. loss of pigment is also the clinical problem such as vitiligo^{27, 28, 29, 30}. Melanin pigments are synthesized in the intracellular organelles of melanocytes called melanosome with the help of melanocyte-specific enzymes, namely tyrosinase, tyrosinase-related protein 1(TRP-1) and tyrosinase related protein-2 (TRP-2) ^{26, 31}. The rate limiting enzyme tyrosinase convert the tyrosine into Dihydroxyphenylalanine (DOPA) followed by dopaquinone and subsequently dopachrome, which is finally converted in to 5, 6 dihydroxyindole in the presence of TRP-1 and TRP-2. Microphthalmia-associated transcription factor (MITF) play key role in melanogenic processes in regulating the gene expression of three enzymes ^{26, 32, 33}. The signaling pathway to induce melanin synthesis is the intracellular cyclic adenosine mono phosphate (cAMP)-mediated pathway which increase MITF expression through activation of the cAMP-response element binding protein (CREB) transcription factor ³². According to recent investigation, members of a family the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) i.e. serine/threonine kinases, including p38 MAPK, extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK), and c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) are activated by various stimuli to influence MITF expression regulation ^{33,34, 35}. Pro inflammatory cytokines and environmentally induced

stresses such as UV irradiation, heat and DNA damage stimulate JNK and p38 MAPK to activate MITF where as ERK phosphorylation suppress MITF expression and hence reduce melanin synthesis ^{36, 37}.

Figure 3: Signal pathways for melanogenesis.

1.3 The objective of this study

Various scientific reports of biological and phytochemical research have been published regarding anti-melanogenic activity from plant. Metabolic disorders, oxidative stress-mediated disorders, hormonal changes, skin irritation, some diseases such as Peutz-Jeghers syndrome and other various environmental factors frequently induce hyper pigmentation which is serious clinical problem. Although some natural bioactive compounds, such as hydroquinone, kojic acid, arbutin, and phenylthiourea, have been utilized for the pigment disorders, none of them are clinically safe due to their adverse effect.

Thus, primary objective of this study was to isolate components from *Lycopus lucidus* and elucidate their chemical structure utilizing various spectroscopic methods. The secondary objective is to investigate anti-melanogenic activity of all isolated compounds.

2. Experiments

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Plant material of *Lycopus lucidus*

The aerial parts of *L. lucidus* were collected from “The private herb garden’ in Yuseong-gu, Daejeon, Republic of Korea, in May 2016. The origin of this plant was confirmed by Prof. K. H. Bae, Chungnam National University. A voucher specimen (KRIB0071766) was deposited at the herbarium of the Korea Research Institute of Bioscience and Biotechnology.

2.2.2 Reagents

2.2.2.1 Reagents for isolation

Solvents for extraction and isolation (methanol, acetonitrile, *n*-butanol, ethyl acetate, chloroform, *n*-hexane etc.) were purchased from SK chemicals (Republic of Korea) and Wintech (Republic of Korea) and used after re-distillation. HPLC solvents were obtained from Budrick and Jackson (Republic of Korea). UPLC solvents were purchased from Wintech (Republic of Korea). LC-MS solvents (Acetonitrile for LC-MS, CHROMASOLV ®) were bought from Fluka, Analytical. Solvent for NMR (CDCl₃, MeOD, DMSO-*d*₆) were purchased from Cell Bio (Republic of Korea).

2.2 Instruments

NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian UNITY 400 (Varian, Inc., Palo Alto, CA) and Bruker DMX-800 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer with the tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. HR-ESIMS were performed with on a Waters Q-ToF Premier spectrometer (Micromass UK Ltd., Manchester, UK) and HR-EIMS (JEOL, Tokyo, Japan) were carried out with JEOL JMS AX505W spectrometer. Sephadex LH-20 (25-100 μm, Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany), silica gel (230-400 mesh, SiliCycle Inc., Quebec, Canada), RP-C18 (Cosmosil 40C₁₈-PREP, Kyoto, Japan) were used for

column chromatography. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on precoated Kiesel-gel 60 F₂₅₄ (0.25 mm, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and Kiesel-gel 60 RP-18F_{254s} (0.25 mm, Merck, Steinheim, Germany). HPLC was performed with an Agilent Technology model 1260 Infinity equipped with 1260 degasser, 1260 Bin pump VL, 1260 ALS, 1260 TCC, and 1260 DAD and Thermo Dionex Ultimate 3000 equipped with Ultimate 3000 pump, Ultimate 3000 auto sampler, Ultimate 3000 column compartment and Ultimate 3000 diode array detector. Analytical Columns: YMC Trait C18 ExRS 5 μ M, 250 \times 4.6 mm, Atlantis T3 5 μ M, 250 \times 4.6 mm, Phenomenex synergy RP-Polar 5 μ M, 250 \times 4.6 mm, Thermo acclaim polar advantage-5 μ M, 250 \times 4.6 mm. UPLC was performed on a model Water ACQUITY UPLC[®] System with PDA Detector. Column: ACQUITY UPLC[®] BEH C18 1.7 μ M, 2.1 \times 10.0 mm. Preparative HPLC was carried out with a model Gilson PLC 2020. Preparative Columns: Atlantis 5 μ M 250 \times 19 mm, Phenomenex synergy RP-Polar 5 μ M, 250 \times 19 mm, Thermo acclaim polar advantage 5 μ M, 250 \times 21.2 mm and YMC Trait C18 ExRS 5 μ M, 250 \times 20 mm.

2.3 Extraction and isolation of *Lycopus lucidus*

Air-dried aerial parts of *Lycopus lucidus* (3.5 kg) were extracted with methanol (9 L) at room temperature five times to obtain 388 g of a solid extract. The methanolic extract (388 g) was suspended in distilled water and then partitioned with hexane, ethyl acetate and saturated butanol to get 60 g of a hexane-soluble extract, 49 g of ethyl acetate soluble extract, 45 g of butanol soluble extract and 142 g of an aqueous extract respectively

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of extraction and fractionation of aerial parts of *Lycopus lucidus*

2.4 Compound separation from ethyl acetate fraction

From the data of HPLC and TLC, ethyl acetate fraction was shown to contain major compounds. The ethyl acetate fraction (35 g) was applied to reverse phase open column (10.5cm×35 cm, 2.8 kg of RP-C18 gel) and eluted with a stepwise gradient of methanol in distilled water (20%, 30%, 40%,50%, 60%, 70% 80%, and 90% methanol each 8 L), yielding 10 sub fractions (denoted by SR-EA-F1 to SR-EA-F10). Compound **1** (29 mg) was obtained from fraction SR-EA-F3 (455 mg) using PLC (5%-50% acetonitrile, gradient, Thermo acclaim polar advantage 5 μM, 250x21.2 mm). Compound **2** (13 mg) and compound **3** (11 mg) were separated from fraction SR-EA-F4 (579 mg) through PLC (5%-95% acetonitrile, gradient, Thermo acclaim polar advantage 5 μM, 250x21.2 mm). Compound **4** (17 mg) was isolated from fraction SR-EA-F5 (345 mg) using PLC again (7%-75% acetonitrile, gradient, Thermo acclaim polar advantage 5 μM, 250x21.2 mm). Fraction SR-EA-F6 (412 mg) and SR-EA-F7 (613 mg) both were subjected to Sephadex LH-20 (100% methanol as an eluent) separately. Fraction SR-EA-F6 yield compound **5**. PLC analysis (7%-75% acetonitrile gradient, YMC Trait C18 ExRS 5 μM, 250x20 mm.) of fraction SR-EA-F7 (932 mg) resulted impure fraction SR-EA-F7.1 and pure compound **8** (15 mg). Fraction SR-EA-F7.1 again subjected for PLC with different method, (5%-70% acetonitrile gradient, YMC Trait C18 ExRS 5 μM, 250x20 mm) to give compound **6** (93 mg) and compound **7** (115 mg). Fraction SR-EA-F8 (899 mg) was undergone through Sephadex LH-20 (100% methanol as an eluent) to give UV-non active subfraction SR-EA-F8.1 (456 mg) and UV active sub fraction SR-EA-F8.2. Compound **9** (75 mg) and compound **10** (2.5mg) were obtained through NP open column chromatography (5 cm × 45 cm; 300 g of silica gel; hexane:EtOAc at 3:7) and Compound **11** (123 mg) was obtained from sub fraction SR-EA-F8.2 by PLC analysis (5%-95% acetonitrile gradient, YMC Trait C18 ExRS 5 μM, 250x20 mm). Fraction SR-EA-F9 (279 mg) and Fraction SR-EA-F10 (3.1 g) were also subjected to NP open column chromatography (5 cm × 45 cm; 300 g of silica gel; hexane: EtOAc at 4:6) and (5 cm × 45 cm; 300 g of silica gel; hexane: EtOAc at

1:1) respectively. Fraction SR-EA-F9 resulted compound **12** (21 mg) whereas compound **13** (25 mg) and compound **14** (3 mg) were isolated from Fraction SR-EA-F10.

Figure 5: Schematic diagram of extraction and isolation of compounds from aerial parts of *Lycopodium lucidus*

2.5 Biological activity

2.5.1 Tyrosinase enzyme activity assay

All the compounds were dissolved in DMSO and used for the experiment at concentrations of 1000 µg/mL. Tyrosinase inhibitory activity assay was performed by previous method with slight modification^{38, 39}. The assay mixtures consisting of 110 µL of 0.1 M phosphate buffer at P^H 6.8 and 10 µL of enzyme solution (Tyrosinase1, 500 µg/mL in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 6.8) was prepared immediately before use. After pre incubation, sample with different concentration (1000, 500, 250, 100, 50, 25 µg/mL) were added and the reaction was initiated by the addition of 20 µL of substrate solution (1.5 mM -Tyrosine in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 6.8). The assay mixture was incubated at 37°C for 15 min, and finally the absorbance at 490 nm was measured with a Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer.

Arbutin is known as tyrosinase inhibitor, which was used as positive control. Tyrosinase inhibitory activity was expressed as the percentage activity of enzyme tyrosinase in the above assay method calculated as $(B-B') / (A-A') \times 100$, where *A* and *B* are the absorbance of the enzyme without and with test material and *A'* and *B'* is without sample as control.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. NMR data of known compounds

3.1.1 Protocatechuic acid (1)

White gray crystalline powder

HR-ESI-MS m/z : 153.12[M-H]⁻

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 7.33 (1H, d, J = 2.0 Hz, H-2), 7.28 (1H, dd, J = 2.0, 8.2 Hz, H-6), 6.77 (H, d, J = 8.0 Hz, H-5). (Appendex 1).

¹³C-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- *d*₆) δ : 167.3 (-COOH, C-7), 155.0 (C-4), 144.9 (C-3), 121.9 (C-5), 121.7 (C-1), 116.5 (C2), 115.1 (6) ⁴⁰. (Appendex 1).

3.1.2 Protocatechualdehyde (2)

White gray crystalline powder

HR-ESI-MS m/z : 137.0251[M-H]⁻

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 9.69 (1H, s, H-7), 7.25 (1H, d, J = 8.0 Hz, H-6), 7.22 (1H, s, H-2), 6.90 (H, s, H-5). (Appendex 2).

¹³C-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- *d*₆) δ : 190.0 (-CHO, C-7), 152.1 (C-4), 145.8 (C-3), 129.8 (C-5), 124.49 (C-1), 115.5 (C2), 114.3 (6) ⁴⁰. (Appendex 2).

3.1.3 Methyl 3, 4 dihydroxy benzoate (3)

White gray crystalline powder

HR-ESI-MS m/z : 167.148[M-H]⁻

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 7.43 (1H, dd, J = 2.0, 8.0z, H-6), 7.42 (1H, s, H-2), 6.83 (1H, d, J = 8.8 Hz, H-5), 3.801 (3H, s-OCH₃, H-8). (Appendex 3).

¹³C-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 167.12 (Carbonyl carbon), 151.01 (C-4), 147.18 (C-3), 123.44 (C-1), 121.74 (C-6), 114.98 (C-5), 112.71 (C-2), 55.526 (-OCH₃, C-7)⁴¹. (Appendix 3).

3.1.4 Para-hydroxy benzoic acid (4)

White crystalline powder

HR-ESI-MS *m/z*: 137.12[M-H]⁻

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 7.78 (2H, d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, H-3& H-5), 6.81 (2H, d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, H-2& H-6). (Appendix 4).

¹³C-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 167.1 (-COOH), 161.5 (C-4), 131.5 (C-2& C6), 121.4 (C-1), 115.0 (C-3&C5)⁴². (Appendix 4).

3.1.5 Caffeic acid (5)

White crystalline powder

HR-ESI-MS *m/z*: 179.159[M-H]⁻

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, Methanol- *d*₄) δ: 7.55 (1H, d, *J* = 15.6 Hz, H-7), 7.07 (1H, d, *J* = 2.0 Hz, H-2), 6.95 (1H, dd, *J* = 2.0 Hz, 8.4 Hz H-6), 6.81 (1H, d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, H-5), 6.224 (1H, d, *J* = 15.6 Hz, H-8). (Appendix 5).

¹³C-NMR (400 MHz, Methanol- *d*₄) δ: 171.2 (C-9), 149.5 (C-4), 147.0 (C-7), 146.9 (C-3), 127.9 (C-1), 122.9 (C-6), 116.6 (C-5), 115.7 (C-8), 115.2 (C-2)⁴³. (Appendix 5).

3.1.6 Rosmarinic acid (6)

White crystalline powder

HR-ESI-MS *m/z*: 359.29[M-H]⁻

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, Methanol- *d*₄) δ: 7.51 (1H, d, *J* = 15.5 Hz, H-7'), 7.03 (1H, d, *J* = 2.0 Hz, H-2'), 6.82 (1H, dd, *J* = 2.0, 8.5 Hz, H-6'), 6.72 (1H, d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, H-5'), 6.66 (1H, d, *J* = 2.0 Hz, H-2),

6.64 (1H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, H-5), 6.57 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0, 8$ Hz, H-6), 6.28 (1H, d, $J = 15.5$ Hz, H-8'), 5.20 (1H, dd, $J = 5.0, 7.5$ Hz, H-8), 3.06 (1H, dd, $J = 5.5, 14.5$ Hz, H-7a), 3.00 (1H, dd, $J = 5.5, 14.5$ Hz, H-7b) (Appendex 6).

^{13}C -NMR (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ : 171.3 (C-9), 166.8 (C-9'), 149.1 (C-4'), 146.6 (C-7'), 146.4 (C-3'), 145.8 (C-3), 144.9 (C-4), 129.1 (C-1), 127.3 (C-1'), 121.5 (C-6'), 117.3 (C-6), 116.6 (C-2), 115.6 (C-5'), 116.4 (C-5), 114.3 (C-2'), 114.2 (C-8'), 73.8 (C-8), 37.0 (C-7) ⁴⁴. (Appendex 6).

3.1.7 Methyl rosmarinate (7)

White crystalline powder

HR-ESI-MS m/z : 373.24[M-H]⁻

^1H -NMR (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ : 7.55 (1H, d, $J = 15.5$ Hz H-7'), 7.04 (1H, d, $J = 2$ Hz, H-2'), 6.95 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0, 8.5$ Hz, H-6'), 6.78 (1H, d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, H-5'), 6.70 (1H, d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, H-2), 6.69 (1H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, H-5), 6.57 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0, 8.0$ Hz, H-6), 6.26 (1H, d, $J = 15.5$ Hz, H-8'), 5.19 (1H, dd, $J = 5.0, 7.5$ Hz, H-8), 3.7 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.06 (1H, dd, $J = 5.5, 14.5$ Hz, H-7a), 3.00 (1H, dd, $J = 5.5, 14.5$ Hz, H-7b). (Appendex 7).

^{13}C -NMR (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ : 172.3 (C-9), 168.4 (C-9'), 149.9 (C-4'), 148.1 (C-7'), 146.9 (C-3'), 146.3 (C-3), 145.5 (C-4), 128.8 (C-1), 127.7 (C-1'), 123.3 (C-6'), 121.9 (C-6), 117.6 (C-2), 116.6 (C-5'), 116.4 (C-5), 115.3 (C-2'), 114.2 (C-8'), 74.8 (C-8), 52.8 (-OCH₃), 38.0 (C-7) ⁴⁴. (Appendex 7).

3.1.8 Quercetin 3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (8)

Yellow crystalline powder

HR-ESI-MS m/z : 463.371[M-H]⁻

^1H -NMR (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ : 7.71 (1H, d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, H-6), 7.58 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 8.4$ Hz, H-

6'), 6.87 (1H, d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, H-5'), 6.39 (1H, s, H-8), 6.20 (1H, s, H-6), 5.25 (1H, d, $J = 7.6$ Hz, galactose H-1), 3.37-3.60 (4H, m, sugar protons). (Appendix 8).

^{13}C -NMR (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ : 179.6 (C-4), 166.1 (C-7), 163.2 (C-5), 159.1 (C-2), 158.5 (C-9), 149.9 (C-4'), 146.0 (C-3'), 135.7 (C-3), 123.3 (C-6'), 123.2 (C-1'), 117.6 (C-5'), 116.1 (C-2), 105.8 (C-10), 104.4 (galactose-C-1), 100.0 (C-6), 94.8 (C-8), 78.5 (galactose-C-3), 78.2 (galactose-C5), 75.8 (galactose-C2), 71.3 (galactose-C4), 62.7 (galactose-C6)⁴⁴. (Appendix 8).

3.1.9 Luteolin (11)

Yellow amorphous powder

HR-ESI-MS m/z : 185.24[M-H]⁻

^1H -NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 12.97 (s, -OH), 7.42 (1H, d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, H-6'), 7.39 (1H, s, H-2'), 6.88 (1H, d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, H-5'), 6.66 (1H, s, H-3), 6.43 (1H, s, H-8), 6.18 (1H, s, H-6). (Appendix 9).

^{13}C -NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 181.6 (C-4), 164.1 (C-7), 163.8 (C-2), 161.4 (C-5), 157.2 (C-9), 149.7 (C-4'), 145.7 (C-3'), 121.4 (C-1'), 118.9 (C-6'), 115.9 (C-5'), 113.3 (C-2'), 103.6 (C-10), 102.8 (C-3), 98.82 (C-6), 93.8 (C-8)⁴⁴. (Appendix 9).

3.2 Structure elucidation of new compounds from *Lycopus lucidus*

3.2.1 Structure elucidation of compound **9**

Compound **9** was obtained as white crystalline needle. Its molecular formula $C_{20}H_{34}O_4$ was deduced by using HR-ESI-MS $[M-H]^-$ ion at m/z 337.2325. The 1H NMR showed three olefin protons at δ_H 5.78 (1H, dd, $J = 10.8, 17.2$ Hz, H-15), 4.90 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16a) and 4.79 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16b). Twelve methylene groups were found at δ_H 1.70 (1H, m, H-1a), 1.22 (1H, m, H1b), 1.94 (1H, m, H-2a), 1.50 (1H, m, H-2b), 1.78 (1H, m, H-6a), 1.45 (1H, m, H-6b), 1.42 (2H, m, H-7), 2.38 (1H, ddd, $J = 2.8, 2.4, 13.2$ Hz, H-11a), 1.56 (1H, m, H-11b), 2.015 (1H, d, $J = 14.4$ Hz, H-14a) and 1.19 (1H, m, H-14b) along with two oxygenated geminal methylene protons at δ_H 3.89 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18a) and 3.54 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18b). Beside these, oxygenated methine protons at δ_H 3.39-3.41 (2H, m, H-3 and H-12) and other two normal methine protons at δ_H 2.07 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0, 12.6$ Hz, H-5) and 1.91 (1H, m, H-9) were detected. The 1H NMR also showed the presence of methyl protons at δ_H 1.24 (3H, s, H-19), 1.01 (3H, s, H-20) and 0.92 (3H, s, H-17). The ^{13}C - NMR exhibited 20 carbon signals consisting of two olefin carbon signals at δ_C 153.4 (C-15) and 108.9 (C-16), four oxygenated carbon signals at δ_C 75.6 (C-12), 74.9 (C-8-Tertiary carbon), 68.5 (C-3) and 64.5 (C-18). Three methyl signal were detected at δ_C 33.7 (C-17), 25.0 (C-19) and 22.1 (C-20). Similarly other six normal methylene carbons at δ_C 36.7 (C-1), 28.5 (C-2), 17.9 (C-6), 39.2 (C-7), 27.1 (C-11) and 45.9 (C-14), two normal methine carbon signals at δ_C 43.9 (C-5) and 40.5 (C-9) were also recorded. Four carbon signal at δ_C 74.8 (C-8), 45.5 (C-4), 37.7 (C-13) and 33.9 (C-10) were found to be tertiary carbons through HMQC analysis. All protons were assigned to their corresponding carbons using HMQC experiment. Analysis of the 1H - 1H COSY plot of compound **9** suggested correlations (H1/H2/H3), (H5/H6/H7), (H9/H11/H12) and (H15/H16). In the HMBC data, correlations (C-11 and C-13)/H-12), (C-8/H-7) and ((C-18/(H-5 and H-3)) confirmed the positions of four hydroxyl groups, also carbon-proton correlations (C-17/H-15) and (C-20/H-1) ensured the exact position of C-17 and C-20 methyl group respectively. Presence of hydroxyl group at C-8 was

confirmed as it was tertiary oxygenated carbon. Relative configuration of compound was confirmed by ROESY analysis. . Relative configuration of compound was confirmed by ROESY analysis. Configuration of H-17 methyl group was found to be at α position through the observation of difference in chemical shift of α C-17 and β C-17 in the literature ⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹. Similarly configuration of 8-hydroxyl group ensured to be at β position by correlating with chemical shift of C-17 methyl group (trans configuration δ C-17 > 32 ppm, cis relationships δ C-17 < 25 ppm) ^{46, 50}. Using this configuration as a reference, relative configuration of H-3, H-5, H-9, H-12 and H-20 was confirmed from the correlation as follow, (H-17 to H-11b), (H-11b to H-12), which confirmed hydroxyl group at C-12 should to be at β position, correlation (H-11a to H-20) ensured β position of H-20, correlation (H-11b to H-9) and (H-9 to H-5) indicated α position of their proton, finally corellations (H-9 to H-6a), (H-6a to H-18b) and (H-18b to H-3) ensured the β position of C-3 hydroxyl group. Therefore, chemical structure of compound **9** was established as 3 β , 8 β , 12 β , 18-tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en.

Table 2: ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR spectroscopic data of compound 9 in Methanol- d_4

Carbon position	^1H -NMR (δ_{H})	^{13}C -NMR (δ_{C})
1	1.70 (1H, m, H-1a) 1.22 (1H, m, H-1b)	36.7
2	1.94 (1H, m, H-2a) 1.50 (1H, m, H-2b)	28.5
3	3.39-3.42 (1H, m, H-3)	68.5
4		46.5
5	2.07 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0, 12.6$ Hz, H-5)	43.9
6	1.78 (1H, m, H-6a) 1.45 (1H, m, H-6b)	17.9
7	1.42 (2H, m, H-7)	39.2
8		74.9
9	1.91 (1H, m, H-9)	40.5
10		33.9
11	2.38 (1H, ddd, $J = 2.8, 2.4, 13.2$ Hz, H-11a) 1.56 (1H, m, H-11b)	27.1
12	3.39-3.42 (1H, m, H-12)	75.6
13		37.7
14	2.015 (1H, d, $J = 14.4$ Hz, H-14a) 1.19 (1H, m, H-14b)	45.9
15	5.78 (1H, dd, $J = 10.8, 17.2$ Hz, H-15)	153.4
16	4.90 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16a) 4.79 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16b)	108.9
17	0.92 (3H, s, H-17)	33.7
18	3.89 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18a) 3.54 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18b)	64.6
19	1.24 (3H, s, H-19)	25.0
20	1.01 (3H, s, H-20)	22.1

Symbols: s, singlet; t, triplet; td, triple doublet, doublet; m, multiplet δ values in ppm, the coupling

constant (J) in Hz

Figure 6: ^{13}C - NMR of compound 9 (400 MHz, $\text{Methanol-}d_4$)

Figure 7: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of compound 9 (400 MHz, $\text{Methanol-}d_4$)

Single Mass Analysis

Tolerance = 10.0 PPM / DBE: min = -1.5, max = 50.0

Element prediction: Off

Number of isotope peaks used for i-FIT = 3

Monoisotopic Mass, Even Electron Ions

65 formula(e) evaluated with 1 results within limits (up to 50 closest results for each mass)

Elements Used:

Mass	Calc. Mass	mDa	PPM	DBE	Formula	i-FIT	i-FIT Norm	Fit Conf %	C	H	O
337.2354	337.2379	-2.5	-7.4	4.5	C20 H33 O4	110.1	n/a	n/a	20	33	4

Figure 8: Mass spectrum of compound 9

Figure 9: HMBC spectrum of compound 9 400 MHz, Methanol- d_4)

Figure 10: COSY spectrum of compound 9 (400 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄)

Figure 11: HMBC spectrum of compound 9 (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4)

Figure 12: ROESY spectrum of compound 9 (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4) (3β , 8β , 12β , 18-tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en)

3.1.2 Structure elucidation of compound 10

Compound **10** was obtained as white crystalline needle. Its molecular formula $C_{20}H_{34}O_4$ was deduced by using HR-ESI-MS $[M-H]^-$ ion at m/z 337.2322. Spectral data of compound **10** was similar with those of compound **9** except chemical shift values. The 1H NMR showed three olefin protons at δ_H 5.91 (1H, dd, $J = 10.8, 17.2$ Hz, H-15), 5.006 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 14.2$ Hz, H-16a) and 4.97 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 7.6$ Hz, H-16b). Twelve methylene groups were found at δ_H 1.51 (1H, m, H-1a), 0.93 (1H, m, H-1b), 1.60 (1H, m, H-2a), 1.43 (1H, m, H-2b), 1.46 (1H, m, H-3a), 1.27 (1H, m, H-3b), 2.04 (1H, m, H-6a), 1.54 (1H, m, H-6b), 2.41 (1H, ddd, $J = 2.8, 2.4, 13.2$ Hz, H-11a), 1.56 (1H, m, H-11b), 2.34 (1H, d, $J = 14.2$, H-14a) and 1.09 (1H, dd $J = 0.8, 14.4$ Hz, H-14b) along with two oxygenated geminal methylene protons at δ_H 3.97 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18a) and 4.50 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18b). Beside these, oxygenated methine protons at δ_H 3.57 (H, t, H-7), 3.48 (1H, m, H-12) and other two normal methine protons at δ_H 1.65 (1H, m, H-9) and 1.92 (1H, m, H-5) were detected. The proton NMR also showed the presence of methyl protons at δ_H 1.23 (3H, s, H-19), 1.01 (3H, s, H-20) and 0.912 (3H, s, H-17). The ^{13}C -NMR exhibited 20 carbon signals consisting of two olefin carbon signals at δ_C 149.7 (C-15) and 111.8 (C-16), four oxygenated carbon signals at δ_C 75.7 (C-12), 75.1 (C-7) 74.1 (C-8-Tertiary carbon), and 64.5 (C-18). Three methyl signal were detected at δ_C 33.9 (C-17), 26.1 (C-19) and 22.2 (C-20). Similarly other six normal methylene carbons at δ_C 37.7 (C-1), 20.7 (C-2), 43.5 (C-3), 25.3 (C-6), 27.4 (C-11) and 39.4 (C-14), two normal methine carbon signals at δ_C 48.0 (C-5) and 44.8 (C-9) were also recorded. Four carbon signal at δ_C 74.1 (C-8), 42.0 (C-4), 41.5 (C-13) and 33.9 (C-10) were found to be tertiary carbons through HMQC analysis. All protons were assigned to their corresponding carbons using HMQC experiment. Analysis of the 1H - 1H COSY plot of compound **10** suggested correlations (H1/H2/H3), (H5/H6/H7), (H9/H11/H12) and (H15/H16). Relative configuration of compound was confirmed by ROESY analysis. Configuration of H-17 methyl group was found to be at α position through the observation of difference in chemical shift of α C-17 and β C-17 in the literature⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹. Similarly configuration of 8-hydroxyl group ensured to be at β position by correlating with chemical shift of C-17 methyl group (trans configuration δ_C -17 > 32

ppm, cis relationships $\delta C-17 < 25$ ppm)^{46, 50}. Using this configuration as a reference, relative configuration of H-5, H-7, H-9, H-12 and H-20 was confirmed from the correlation as follow, (H-17 to H-11b), (H-11b to H-12), which confirmed hydroxyl group at C-12 should be at β position, correlation (H-11a to H-20) ensured β position of H-20, correlations (H-11b to H-9), (H-9 to H-5) and (H-5 to H-6a) indicated α position of their proton, proton H-6b which is at β showed correlation with H-7, which means proton of C-7 have β position and hence hydroxyl group of C-7 must have α orientation. Therefore chemical structure of compound **10** was established as $7\alpha, 8\beta, 12\beta, 18$ -tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en.

Table 3: ¹H and ¹³C-NMR spectroscopic data of compound 10 in Methanol- *d*₄

Carbon position	¹ H-NMR (δ _H)	¹³ C-NMR (δ _C)
1	1.51 (1H, m, H-1a)	37.7
	0.93 (1H, m, H-1b)	
2	1.60 (1H, m, H-2a)	20.7
	1.43 (1H, m, H-2b)	
3	1.46 (1H, m, H-3a)	43.5
	1.27 (1H, m, H-3b)	
4		42.0
5	1.92 (1H, m, H-5)	44.4
6	2.04 (1H, m, H-6a)	25.9
	1.54 (1H, m, H-6b)	
7	3.57 (1H, t, H-7)	75.1
8		74.12
9	1.65 (1H, m, H-9)	48.0
10		34.0
11	2.414 (1H, td (J=2.8 Hz, 2.4 Hz, 13.2 Hz, H-11a)	27.4
	1.56 (1H,m-H11b)	
12	3.48 (1H, m, H-12)	75.7
13	1.70 (1H, m, H-1a)	41.5
14	2.347(1H, d, J=14.4 Hz, H-14a)	39.4
	1.098 (1H, dd, J= 0.8 Hz, 14.4 Hz, H-14b)	
15	5.91 (1H, dd, J=10.8 Hz, 17.2 Hz, H-15)	149.7
16	5.00 (1H, dd, J=1.2 Hz, 14.2 Hz, H-16a)	111.8
	4.97 (1H, dd, J=1.2 Hz, 7.6 Hz, H-16b)	
17	0.912 (3H, s, H-17)	33.9
18	4.50 (1H, d, J=12 Hz, H-18a)	64.5
	3.487 (1H, d, J=12 Hz, H-18b)	
19	1.26 (3H, s, H-19)	26.1
20	1.01(3H,s, H-20)	22.29

Symbols: s, singlet; t, triplet, td; triple doublet, doublet; m, multiplet δ values in ppm, the coupling

constant (J) in Hz

Figure 13: ^{13}C -NMR of compound 10 (400 MHz, $\text{Methanol-}d_4$)

Figure 14: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4)

Figure 15:- Mass spectrum of compound 10

Figure 16: HMQC spectrum of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄)

Figure 17: COSY spectrum of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄)

Figure 18: HMBC spectrum of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4)

Figure 19: ROESY spectrum of compound 10 (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4) (7α , 8β , 12β , 18-tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en)

3.2.3 Structure elucidation of compound 12

Compound **12** was obtained as white amorphous powder. Its molecular formula $C_{20}H_{34}O_5$ was deduced by using HR-ESI-MS $[M-H]^-$ ion at m/z 353.2325. Spectral data of compound **12** was similar with those of compound **9** except one proton of C-11 was substituted by hydroxyl group. The 1H NMR showed three olefin protons at δ_H 5.76 (1H, dd, $J = 10.8, 17.2$ Hz, H-15), 4.88 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16a) and 4.79 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16b). Ten methylene groups were found at δ_H 1.83 (1H, m, H-1a), 1.14 (1H, m, H-1b), 1.97 (1H, m, H-2a), 1.56 (1H, m, H-2b), 1.76 (1H, m, H-6a), 1.48 (1H, m, H-6b), 1.43 (2H, m, H-7), 1.93 (1H, m, H-14a) and 1.26 (1H, m, H-14b) along with two oxygenated germinal methylene protons at δ_H 3.85 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18a) and 3.54 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18b). Beside these, three oxygenated methine proton signals at δ_H 4.1 (H, t, H-11), 3.59 (1H, t, H-3) and 3.29 (1H, m, H-12) and other two normal methine protons at δ_H 2.15 (1H, dd, $J = 2, 0, 12.6$ Hz, H-5) and 2.03 (1H, d, $J = 2.8$ Hz, H-9) were detected. The 1H NMR also showed the presence of three methyl protons at δ_H 1.25 (3H, s, H-20), 1.24 (3H, s, H-19) and 1.00 (3H, s, H-17). The ^{13}C -NMR exhibited 20 carbon signals consisting of two olefin carbon signals at δ_C 153.4 (C-15) and 109.0 (C-16), five oxygenated carbon signals at δ_C 77.5 (C-12), 74.8 (C-8-Tertiary carbon), 73.1 (C-11), 68.0 (C-3) and 62.3 (C-18). Three methyl signal were detected at δ_C 33.4 (C-17), 25.0 (C-19) and 24.5 (C-20). Similarly other five normal methylene carbons at δ_C 37.6 (C-1), 28.4 (C-2), 17.6 (C-6), 39.0 (C-7) and 46.1 (C-14), two normal methine carbon signals at δ_C 43.4 (C-5) and 44.2 (C-9) were also recorded. Four carbon signal at δ_C 74.8 (C-8), 48.23 (C-4), 38.3 (C-13) and 34.6 (C-10) were found to be tertiary carbons through HMQC analysis. All protons were assigned to their corresponding carbons using HMQC experiment. Analysis of the 1H - 1H COSY plot of compound **12** suggested correlations (H-1/H-2/H-3), (H-5/H-6/H-7), (H-9/H-11/H-12) and (H-15/H-16). In the HMBC data, correlations ((C-9 and C-12)/H-11), (C-8/H-7) and (C-18/(H-5 and H-3)) confirmed the positions of four hydroxyl groups, also carbon-proton correlations (C-17/H-13) and (C-20/H-9) ensured the exact position of C-17 and C-20 methyl group respectively. Presence of hydroxyl group at C-8 was confirmed as it was tertiary oxygenated carbon. Relative configuration of Compound was

confirmed by ROESY analysis Configuration of H-17 methyl group was found to be at α position through the observation of difference in chemical shift of α C-17 and β C-17 in the literature ⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹. Similarly configuration of 8-hydroxyl group ensured to be at β position by correlating with chemical shift of C-17 methyl group (trans configuration δ C-17 > 32 ppm, cis relationships δ C-17 < 25 ppm) ⁴⁶. ⁵⁰. Using this configuration as a reference, relative configuration of H-3, H-5, H-9, H-11, H-12 and H-20 was confirmed from the correlation as follow, (H-17 to H11), (H-11 to H-5), which confirmed hydroxyl group at C-11 is at β position. Similarly proton of C-12 didn't show any relationship with α proton of C-11, it must be in β orientation, which confirmed hydroxyl group of C-12 have α orientation. Proton of C-20 didn't show any correlation with adjacent α proton of C-11 might be due to it's β orientation. Correlation (H-11a to H-9) and (H-9 to H-5) indicated α position of their proton, finally corellations (H-9 to H-6a), (H-6a to H-18b), (H-18b to H-2a) and (H-2b to H-3) ensured the β orientation of C-3 hydroxyl group. Therefore chemical structure of compound 12 was established as - 3 β , 8 β , 11 β , 12 α , 18-pentahydroxy pimar-15-en.

Table 4: ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR spectroscopic data of compound 12 in Methanol- d_4

Carbon position	^1H -NMR (δ_{H})	^{13}C -NMR (δ_{C})
1	1.83 (1H, m, H-1a) 1.14 (1H, m, H-1b)	37.6
2	1.97 (1H, m, H-2a) 1.56 (1H, m, H-2b)	28.4
3	3.59 (1H, t H-3)	68.4
4		48.3
5	2.015 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0, 12.6$ Hz, H-5)	43.4
6	1.76 (1H, m, H-6a) 1.48 (1H, m, H-6b)	17.6
7	1.43 (2H, m, H-7)	39.0
8		74.8
9	2.042, (1H, d $J = 2.8$ Hz, H-9)	44.2
10		34.6
11	4.1 (1H, t, H-11)	73.1
12	3.28 (1H, m, H-12)	77.5
13		38.34
14	1.93 (1H, m, H-14a) 1.26 (1H, m, H-14b)	46.1
15	5.76 (1H, dd, $J = 10.8, 17.2$ Hz, H-15)	153.4
16	4.88 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16a) 4.79 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16b)	109.0
17	1.01 (3H, s, H-17)	33.4
18	3.85 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18a) 3.54 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18b)	62.3
19	1.24 (3H, s H-19)	25.1
20	1.25 (3H, s, H-20)	24.5

Symbols: s, singlet; t, triplet; td; triple doublet, doublet; m, multiplet δ values in ppm, the coupling constant (J) in Hz.

Figure 20: ^{13}C - NMR of compound 12 (400 MHz, $\text{Methanol-}d_4$)

Figure 21: ^1H -NMR of compound 12 (400 MHz, $\text{Methanol-}d_4$)

SR_F39_P1_252 (4.961)

1: TOF MS ES-
764

Figure 22: Mass Spectrum of compound 12

Figure 23: HMBC Correlation of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol-d₄)

Figure 24: COSY Correlation of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4)

Figure 25: HMBC Correlation of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄)

Figure 26: ROESY Correlation of compound 12 (400 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) (3 β , 8 β , 11 β , 12 α , 18-pentahydroxy pimar-15-en)

3.2.4 Structure elucidation of compound 13

Compound **13** was obtained as white crystalline needle. Its molecular formula $C_{22}H_{36}O_5$ was deduced by using HR-ESI-MS $[M-H]^-$ ion at m/z 379.2464. Spectral data of compound **13** was similar with those of compound **9** except there was addition of new methyl proton as an acetyl moiety at δ_H 2.06 (3H, s, H-22), where as there is one new tertiary carbonyl carbons signal at δ_C 172.2 (-CO, C-21) and one methyl carbon at δ_C 22.4 (C-22). This confirms that one proton of compound **9** was substituted by acetyl group. Increment of mass of compound **13** by 42 unit $[-COCH_3-H^+]$ than compound **9** also confirmed this fact. Position of acetyl substitution was confirmed accurately by other 2D NMR analysis.

. The 1H NMR showed three olefin protons at δ_H 5.75 (1H, dd, $J = 10.8, 17.2$ Hz, H-15), 4.86 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16a) and 4.80 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16b). Twelve methylene groups were found at δ_H 1.70 (1H, m, H-1a), 1.20 (1H, m, H-1b), 1.96 (1H, m, H-2a), 1.56 (1H, m, H-2b), 1.76 (1H, m, H-6a), 1.45 (1H, m, H-6b), 1.50 (2H, m, H-7), 2.39 (1H, ddd, $J = 2.8, 2.4, 13.2$ Hz, H-11a), 1.66 (1H, m, H-11b), 1.63 (1H, m, H-14a) and 1.23 (1H, m, H-14b) along with two oxygenated geminal methylene protons at δ_H 3.94 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18a) and 3.56 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18b). Beside these, two oxygenated methine protons at δ_H 3.43 (1H, t, H-3) and 4.62 (1H, t, H-12), other two normal methine protons at δ_H 2.09 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0, 12.6$ Hz, H-5) and 1.84 (1H, m, H-9) were detected. The 1H NMR also showed the presence of four methyl protons at δ_H 2.06 (3H, s, H-22), 1.24 (3H, s, H-19), 1.00 (3H, s, H-20), and 0.84 (3H, s, H-17). The ^{13}C -NMR exhibited 22 carbon signals consisting of one tertiary carbonyl signal at δ_C 172.0 (-CO, C-21), two olefin carbon signals at δ_C 153.0 (C-15) and 109.1 (C-16), four oxygenated carbon signals at δ_C 77.8 (C-12), 73.4 (C8-tertiary carbon), 68.1 (C-3) and 64.4 (C-18). Four methyl signal were detected at δ_C 33.6 (C-17), 25.0 (C-19), 21.8 (C-20) and 21.4 (C-22). Similarly other six normal methylene carbons at δ_C 36.6 (C-1), 28.5 (C-2), 17.8 (C-6), 39.0 (C-7), 27.1 (C-11) and 45.6 (C-14), two normal methine carbon signals at δ_C 45.2 (C-5) and 41.6 (C-9) were also recorded. Four carbon signal at δ_C 73.4 (C-8), 46.2 (C-4), 37.6 (C-13) and 33.8 (C-10) were found to be tertiary carbons through HMQC analysis. All protons were assigned

to their corresponding carbons using HMQC experiment. Analysis of the ^1H - ^1H COSY plot of compound **13** suggested correlations (H-1/H-2/H-3), (H-5/H-6 /H-7), (H-9/H-11/H-12) and (H-15/H-16). In the HMBC data, carbon –proton correlations (C-21/H-22) illustrated that methyl group is attached with carbonyl carbon and also (C-12/H-21) correlation suggest that proton from hydroxyl group of C-12 was substituted by acetyl group, Correlations (C-4/H-18) and (C-3/H-18) confirmed the positions of C-18- hydroxyl group and C-3 hydroxyl group respectively, also carbon-proton correlations (C-13/H-17) and (C-20/H-9) ensured the exact position of C-17 and C-20 methyl groups respectively. Presence of hydroxyl group at C-8 was confirmed as it was tertiary oxygenated carbon. Relative configuration of compound was confirmed by ROESY analysis. Configuration of H-17 methyl group was found to be at α position through the observation of difference in chemical shift of α C-17 and β C-17 in the literature ⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹. Similarly configuration of 8-hydroxyl group ensured to be at β position by correlating with chemical shift of C-17 methyl group (trans configuration $\delta\text{C-17} > 32$ ppm, cis relationships $\delta\text{C-17} < 25$ ppm) ^{46, 50}. Using this configuration as a reference, relative configuration of H-3, H-5, H-9, H-12 and H-20 was confirmed from the correlation as follow, (H-17 to H-11b), (H-11b to H-12), which confirm acetyl group at C-12 is at β position, correlation (H-11a to H-20) ensured β position of H-20, correlation (H-11b to H-9) and (H-9 to H-5) indicated α position of their proton, finally corellations (H-9 to H-6a), (H-6a to H-18b) and (H-18b to H-3) ensured the β position of C-3 hydroxyl group. Therefore chemical structure of compound **13** was established as - 12 β acetoxy, 8 β , 3 β , 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en.

Table 5: ¹H and ¹³C-NMR spectroscopic data of compound 13 in Methanol- *d*₄

Carbon position	¹ H-NMR(δH)	¹³ C-NMR (δC)
1	1.70 (1H, m, H-1a)	36.6
	1.20 (1H, m, H-1b)	
2	1.96 (1H, m, H-2a)	28.4
	1.56 (1H, m, H-2b)	
3	3.43 (1H, m, H-3)	68.1
4		46.2
5	2.03 (1H,dd, <i>J</i> = 2.0, 12.6 Hz, H-5)	45.2
6	1.76 (1H, m, H-6a)	17.8
	1.45 (1H, m, H-6)	
7	1.50 (2H, m, H-7)	39.0
8		73.4
9	1.84 (1H, m, H-9)	41.6
10		33.8
11	2.39 (1H, ddd, <i>J</i> = 2.8, 2.4, 13.2 Hz, H-11a)	24.2
	1.66 (1H, m, H-11b)	
12	4.62 (1H ,t, H-12)	77.8
13		37.6
14	1.63 (1H, m, H-14a)	45.6
	1.23 (1H, m, H-14b)	
15	5.75 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> = 10.8, 17.2 Hz, H-15)	153.0
16	4.86 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> = 1.2, 17.4 Hz, H-16a)	109.1
	4.80 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> = 1.2, 17.4 Hz, H-16b)	
17-CH3	0.84 (3H, s, H-17)	33.6
18	3.94 (1H, d, <i>J</i> = 12.0 Hz, H-18a)	64.4
	3.56 (1H, d, <i>J</i> = 12.0 Hz, H-18b)	
19-CH3	1.24 (3H,s, H-19)	25.0

20-CH3	1.00 (3H, s, H-20)	21.8
21-CO-		172.2
22-OCH3	2.06 (3H, s, H-22)	21.4

Symbols :s, singlet; t, triplet; td; triple doublet, doublet; m, multiplet δ values in ppm, the coupling constant (J) in Hz.

Figure 27: ^{13}C -NMR of compound 13 (400 MHz, $\text{Methanol-}d_4$)

Figure 28: ¹H- NMR of compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol- *d*₄)

Single Mass Analysis

Tolerance = 10.0 PPM / DBE: min = -1.5, max = 50.0

Element prediction: Off

Number of isotope peaks used for i-FIT = 3

Monoisotopic Mass, Even Electron Ions

82 formula(e) evaluated with 1 results within limits (up to 50 closest results for each mass)

Elements Used:

Mass	Calc. Mass	mDa	PPM	DBE	Formula	i-FIT	i-FIT Norm	Fit Conf %	C	H	O
379.2479	379.2484	-0.5	-1.3	5.5	C22 H35 O5	63.8	n/a	n/a	22	35	5

SSR-L-EA-F44-P1 327 (6.450)

1: TOF MS ES-

Figure 29: Mass spectrum of compound 13

Figure 30: HMQC spectrum compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄)

Figure 31: COSY Correlation of compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄)

Figure 32: HMBC Correlation of compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄)

Figure 33: ROESY Correlation of compound 13 (400 MHz, Methanol- d_4) (12 β acetoxy, 8 β , 3 β , 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en)

3.2.5 Structure elucidation of compound 14

Compound **14** was obtained as white crystalline needle. Its molecular formula $C_{22}H_{36}O_5$ was deduced by using HR-ESI-MS $[M-H]^-$ ion at m/z 379.2464. Spectral data of compound **14** was similar with those of compound **13** except position of acetyl substitution and was confirmed accurately by 2D NMR analysis. The 1H NMR showed three olefin protons at δ_H 5.76 (1H, dd, $J = 10.8, 17.2$ Hz, H-15), 4.84 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16a) and 4.74 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16b). Twelve methylene groups were found at δ_H 1.81 (1H, m, H-1a), 1.11 (1H, m, H-1b), 1.83 (1H, m, H-2a), 1.50 (1H, m, H-2b), 1.70 (1H, m, H-6a), 2.00 (1H, m, H-6b), 1.42 (1H, m, H-7a), 1.25 (1H, m, H-7b), 1.93 (1H, m, H-11a), 1.53 (1H, m, H-11b), 2.03 (1H, m, H-14a) and 1.15 (1H, m, H-14b) along with two oxygenated geminal methylene protons at δ_H 5.08 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18a) and 4.52 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18b). Beside these, two oxygenated methine protons at δ_H 4.1 (1H, t, H-3) and 3.49 (1H, m, H-12), other two normal methine protons at δ_H 2.157 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0, 12.6$ Hz, H-9) and 1.96 (1H, m, H-5) were detected. The 1H NMR also showed the presence of four methyl protons at δ_H 1.98 (3H, s, H-22), 1.23 (3H, s, H-19), 0.89 (3H, s, H-20), and 0.88 (3H, s, H-17).

The ^{13}C -NMR exhibited 22 carbon signals consisting of one tertiary carbonyl signal at δ_C 171.1 (-CO, C-21), two olefin carbon signals at δ_C 153.4 (C-15) and 108.3 (C-16), four oxygenated carbon signals at δ_C 75.9 (C8-Tertiary carbon), 75.0 (C-12), 65.9 (C-3) and 65.7 (C-18). Four methyl signal were detected at δ_C 34.1 (C-17), 24.6 (C-19), 22.9 (C-20) and 21.1 (C-22). Similarly other six normal methylene carbons at δ_C 35.1 (C-1), 26.7 (C-2), 19.3 (C-6), 39.3 (C-7), 26.3 (C-11) and 46.9 (C-14), two normal methine carbon signals at δ_C 43.3 (C-5) and 39.8 (C-9) were also recorded. Four carbon signal at δ_C 75.9 (C-8), 45.1 (C-4), 37.3 (C-13) and 32.9 (C-10) were found to be tertiary carbons through HMQC analysis. All protons were assigned to their corresponding carbons using HMQC experiment. Analysis of the 1H - 1H COSY plot of compound **14** suggested correlations (H-1/H-2/H-3), (H-5/H-6/H-7) (H-9/H-11/H-12) and (H-15/H-16). In the HMBC data, carbon-proton correlations (C-21/H-22) illustrated that methyl group is attached with carbonyl carbon and also (C-22/H-18)

correlation suggested that proton from hydroxyl group of C-3 was substituted by acetyl group, Correlations (C-4 and C-5/H18) confirmed the positions of C-18- hydroxyl group. Also carbon-proton correlations (C-13/H-17) and (C-20/H-9) ensured the exact position of C-17 and C-20 methyl groups respectively. Presence of hydroxyl group at C-8 was confirmed as it was oxygenated carbon. Relative configuration of Compound was confirmed by ROESY analysis. Configuration of H-17 methyl group was found to be at α position through the observation of difference in chemical shift of α C-17 and β C-17 in the literature ⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹. Similarly configuration of 8-hydroxyl group ensured to be at β position by correlating with chemical shift of C-17 methyl group (trans configuration δ C-17 > 32 ppm, cis relationships δ C-17 < 25 ppm) ^{46, 50}. Using this configuration as a reference, relative configuration of H-3, H-9, H-12 and H-20 was confirmed from the correlation as follow, (H-17 to H-11b), (H-11b to H-12) confirmed β position of C-12 hydroxyl group. Correlation (H-11b to H-9) and (H-11a to H-20) confirmed α and β position of H-5 and H-20 respectively. Other correlations (H-20 to H-1a), (H-1a to H-2b) and (H-2b to H-3) ensured β position of acetoxy group of C-3. There chemical structure of compound **14** was established as 3 β acetoxy, 8 β , 12 β , 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en.

Table 6: ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR spectroscopic data compound 14 in Acetone- d_6

Carbon position	^1H -NMR(δH)	^{13}C -NMR (δC)
1	1.81 (1H, m, H-1a)	35.1
	1.11 (1H, m, H-1b)	
2	1.83 (1H, m, H-2a)	26.7
	1.50 (1H, m, H-2b)	
3	4.1 (1H,t, H-3)	65.9
4		45.1
5	1.96 (1H, m, H-9)	43.3
6	2.00 (1H, m- H6a)	19.3
	1.70 (1H, m, H-6b)	
7	1.42 (1H, m, H-7a)	39.3
	1.25 (1H, m, H-7b)	
8		75.9
9	2.15 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0, 13.2$ Hz, H-5)	39.8
10		43.4
11	1.93 (1H, m, H-11a)	26.3
	1.53 (1H, m, H-11b)	
12	3.49 (1H, m, H-12)	75.0
13		37.33
14	2.03 (1H, m, H-14a)	46.9
	1.15 (1H, m, H-14b)	
15	5.76 (1H, dd, $J = 10.8, 17.2$ Hz, H-15)	153.4
16	4.84 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16a)	108.3
	4.74 (1H, dd, $J = 1.2, 17.4$ Hz, H-16b)	
17-CH3	0.88 (3H, s, H-17)	34.1
18	5.08 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18a)	65.5
	4.52 (1H, d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, H-18b)	
19-CH3	1.23 (3H,s, H-19)	24.6
20-CH3	0.89 (3H, s, H-20)	22.9

21-CO-		171.1
22-OCH3	1.98 (3H, s, H-22)	21.1

Symbols: s, singlet; br.s, broad singlet; d, doublet; m, multiplet δ values in ppm, the coupling constant (J) in Hz

Figure 34: ^{13}C -NMR of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6)

Figure 35: ¹H-NMR of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone-*d*₆)

Single Mass Analysis

Tolerance = 10.0 PPM / DBE: min = -1.5, max = 50.0

Element prediction: Off

Number of isotope peaks used for i-FIT = 3

Monoisotopic Mass, Even Electron Ions

82 formula(e) evaluated with 1 results within limits (up to 50 closest results for each mass)

Elements Used:

Mass	Calc. Mass	mDa	PPM	DBE	Formula	i-FIT	i-FIT Norm	Fit Conf %	C	H	O
379.2473	379.2484	-1.1	-2.9	5.5	C22 H35 O5	24.5	n/a	n/a	22	35	5

SR_F44_P2_325 (6.414)

1: TOF MS ES-

Figure 36: Mass spectrum of compound 14

Figure 37: HMQC Correlation of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone-*d*₆)

Figure 38: COSY Correlation of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6)

Fi

Figure 39: HMBC Correlation of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6)

Figure 40: ROESY Correlation of compound 14 (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) (3 β acetoxy, 8 β , 12 β , 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en)

Figure 41: Compounds isolated from ethyl acetate fraction of aerial parts of *Lycopus lucidus*.

3.3 Tyrosinase enzyme inhibition by isolated compounds

To investigate the effects on tyrosinase enzyme activity of the compounds isolated from *Lycopodium lucidus*, the spectroscopic assay was carried out and result is described as below. Data are expressed as percentage of tyrosinase enzyme activity inhibition after addition of compound at six different concentrations.

Table 7: Effect of compounds on tyrosinase enzyme activity in percentage at different concentration.

Sample	Tyrosinase inhibition (%) \pm S.D. at different Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ML}$)					
	25($\mu\text{g}/\text{ML}$)	50 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ML}$)	100($\mu\text{g}/\text{ML}$)	250($\mu\text{g}/\text{ML}$)	500($\mu\text{g}/\text{ML}$)	1000($\mu\text{g}/\text{ML}$)
Tyrosinase	0	0	0	0	0	0
Blank	100	100	100	100	100	100
Protocatechuic acid	-3.14 \pm 0.17	-1.39 \pm 0.388	0.80 \pm 2.71	3.59 \pm 2.37	1.6 \pm 2.027	6.74 \pm 2.80
Protocatechualdehyde	24.02 \pm 10.2	42.95 \pm 13.92	70.25\pm 5.34	81.59 \pm 3.06	81.53 \pm 3.96	84.15 \pm 1.76
Methyl3,4, dihydroxy benzoate	0.33 \pm 14.70	3.01 \pm 8.36	4.977 \pm 7.15	7.7 \pm 4.87	7.31 \pm 14.57	18.36 \pm 21.65
P-hydroxy benzoic acid	2.71 \pm 17.72	4.04 \pm 12.03	7.15 \pm 13.88	9.98 \pm 8.32	14.73 \pm 5.99	26.25 \pm 8.02
Caffeic acid	13.67 \pm 17.12	11.06 \pm 16.43	12.98 \pm 7.33	20.44 \pm 5.52	21.81 \pm 11.17	14.37 \pm 1.33
Rosmarinic acid	16.75 \pm 15.78	22.11 \pm 10.78	29.84 \pm 7.80	40.88 \pm 7.76	48.91 \pm 1.98	49.01 \pm 1.63
Methyl rosmarinate	27.04 \pm 7.15	35.92 \pm 16.77	42.2\pm 12.07	55.04\pm 9.7	57.74 \pm 8.34	64.82 \pm 1.81
Quercetin-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside	9.37 \pm 10.43	8.77 \pm 16.69	17.69 \pm 2.28	19.55 \pm 1.76	9.92 \pm 16.13	11.7 \pm 20.18
Luteolin	10.07 \pm 14.01	15.62 \pm 2.63	35.73 \pm 0.77	51.53 \pm 1.42	55.40 \pm 8.02	55.88 \pm 7.01
3 α , 8 β , 12 α , 18-tetrahydroxy-9- <i>epi-ent</i> -pimarane	18.06 \pm 2.84	12.05 \pm 5.69	10.22 \pm 5.17	18.25 \pm 3.32	19.3 \pm 5.65	25.76 \pm 9.74
3 α , 8 β , 11 α , 12 β , 18-pentahydroxy-9- <i>epi-ent</i> -pimarane	18.24 \pm 1.07	14.67 \pm 8.41	16.41 \pm 0.64	18.64 \pm 3.66	18.97 \pm 1.33	20.12 \pm 1.55
12 α acetoxy, 8 β , 3 α , 18-trihydroxy-9- <i>epi-ent</i> -pimarane	15.83 \pm 1.07	16.97 \pm 4.26	16.42 \pm 0.64	18.64 \pm 3.66	24.53 \pm 4.95	31.23 \pm 0.47
Arbutin	13.36 \pm 2.80	18.79 \pm 0.9	25.08\pm 1.29	23.52\pm 2.93	25.21 \pm 0.043	30.77 \pm 1.68

Figure 42:- Inhibition percentage of tyrosinase enzyme activity by isolated compounds in at 250µl/ml and 100µ/ml.

Melanin is synthesized from tyrosine by tyrosinase, tyrosinase related protein 1 (TRP-1) and dopachrome tautomerase (TRP-2) and is closely related to the transcription factor MITF. Tyrosinase is an important enzyme in the process of melanin biosynthesis, which is involved in the cascade reaction in which L-Tyrosine, and L-DOPA act as substrates and this process is the rate-limiting step in melanin biosynthesis. Tyrosinase inhibitors can play great role as a whitening agents. Thus, we investigated the effect on tyrosinase activity of about isolated 12 single compounds from *Lycopus lucidus* including 3 novel compounds. Tyrosinase activity was accessed by monitoring the dopaquinone absorbance at 490 nm, a product of the enzymatic reaction. The oxidation of L-tyrosine catalysed by mushroom tyrosinase can be inhibited by the single compounds in a dose-dependent manner so as to inhibit enzyme activity. The effect of tyrosinase enzyme on the production of dopachrome was proportional to the amount of the enzyme, so the amount of dopachrome in the control without sample was considered as 100% enzymatic activity. Typical tyrosinase inhibitor, arbutin, was used as a competitive inhibitor against L-tyrosine⁴². As shown in table 7, we treated the samples at the concentration of 1000µg/mL, 500 µg/mL, and 250 µg/mL, 100 µg/mL, 50 µg/mL and 25 µg/mL for total 12 compounds and found that compound (2) (Protocatechualdehyde) have

potential inhibitory effect on tyrosinase activity. At concentration of 100µg/mL and 250µg/mL, it inhibited tyrosinase activity by 70.23% and 81.5% respectively. Also, the compound **(7)**, (Methylrosmarinate) found to exhibit effective inhibition of tyrosinase activity by 55.03 % and 64.91 % at the concentration of 100µg/mL and 250µg/mL respectively. Similarly compound **(11)** (Luteolin) also showed effective inhibition of tyrosinase activity by 37.72% and 51.52% at the concentration of 100µg/mL and 250µg/mL respectively. For novel compound **(9)**, enzyme activity inhibition was 10.22% and 18.25 %, whereas, 16.41% and 18.64 % for novel compound **(12)**, similarly 16.42% and 18.648 % for novel compound **(13)** at the concentration of 100µg/mL and 250µg/mL respectively which are comparable to standard arbutin. Many studies has been done regarding tyrosinase inhibitory effect of luteolin and methyl rosmarinate where as further study of Protocatechualdehyde and three novel compound is needed to identify useful whitening agents.

4. Conclusion

- Ethyl acetate fraction of dried aerial parts of *Lycopus lucidus* was subjected for different chromatographic technique to isolate total 14 compounds.
- The separated compounds were analyzed through spectral data such as 1D NMR (^{13}C and ^1H NMR), 2D NMR (HMQC, HMBC, COSY and ROESY), Mass (ESI-MS) and HRESI-TOF-MS.
- Isolated compounds were divided in the class of Polyphenol, flavonoids and diterpenoids.
- Compound (2) (Protocatechualdehyde) and Compound (4) (Methyl 3, 4, dihydroxy benzoate) were isolated for the first time from this plant.
- Compounds 3 β , 8 β , 12 β , 18-tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en (9), 7 α , 8 β , 12 β , 18-tetrahydroxy pimar-15-en (11), 3 β , 8 β , 11 β , 12 α , 18-pentahydroxy pimar-15-en (12), 12 β acetoxy, 8 β , 3 β , 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en (13), 3 β acetoxy, 8 β , 12 β , 18-trihydroxy pimar-15-en (14) were found to be novel compound belonging to the class of pimarane diterpenoids.
- Compound (2) (Protocatechualdehyde) and Compound (7) (Methyl rosmarinate) showed potent inhibitory effect on tyrosinase enzyme activity as compare to positive control arbutin.

5. Appendix

¹H NMR spectrum of Protocatechuic acid (**1**)

^{13}C NMR spectrum of Protocatechuic acid (**1**)

1H NMR spectrum of Protocatechualdehyde (2)

^{13}C NMR spectrum of Protocatechualdehyde (2)

^1H NMR spectrum of 3,4-dihydroxy benzoate (3)

^{13}C NMR spectrum of 3, 4-dihydroxy benzoate (3)

¹H NMR spectrum of Para-hydroxybenzoic acid (4)

^{13}C NMR spectrum of Para-hydroxybenzoic acid (4)

¹H NMR spectrum of Caffeic acid (5)

^{13}C NMR spectrum of Caffeic acid (5)

1H NMR spectrum of Rosmarinic acid (6)

^{13}C NMR of Rosmarinic acid (**6**)

¹H NMR spectrum of Methyl rosmarinate (7)

^{13}C NMR spectrum of Methyl rosmarinate (7)

¹H NMR spectrum of Quercetin 3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside (8)

^{13}C NMR spectrum of Quercetin 3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (**8**)

¹H NMR of Luteolin (11)

^{13}C NMR of Luteolin (11)

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